

LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM
FÜR ARCHÄOLOGIE

Inschriften und der “Knowledge Graph” ... wie CIDOC-CRM als Referenzmodell fungiert ...

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Object-Text-Bild | 28 Apr 2025 | online | 28/04/2025

Teil 2: Hands-On Data-Modellierungen

Ziel sind FAIRe nachvollziehbare Daten in einem Knowledge Graph

F + A = Knowledge Graph | I + R = Linked Open Data / RDF

Samian Research
Online Database

Linked Open Samian Ware
based on LADO and CIDOC CRM

publication via
archaeology.link

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0. Data via Wikidata, CCO and Samian Research, m-DPPL

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interaktionen Anreicherung Experimentell

Endpoint auswählen: Wikidata -> Item types [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick ADD/REMOVE Resource

Queryurlen: ItemLabel Layer Name: Item_label

SPARQL Query:

```

1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wikibase: <http://wikiba.se/ontology#>
4 PREFIX p: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/>
5 PREFIX ps: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/statement/>
6 PREFIX pq: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/qualifier/>
7 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
8 PREFIX bd: <http://www.bigdata.com/rdf#>
9
10 # defaultView: Map["hide": ["?geo"]]
11 # Samian Ware Productioncentres
12 SELECT ?item ?samian ?itemLabel ?geo ?layerLabel ?layer WHERE {
13 ?item wd:P31 wd:Q90412636;
14 wd:P625 ?geo;
15 wd:P2888 ?samian;
16 wd:P706 ?layer.
17 ?item wd:P21 wd:Q102201947.
18 SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
19 }
20

```

Geonames (GNS) FeatureCollections Geometry/C1

- Antarctic field camp (wd:Q471007)
- Antarctic research station (wd:Q149622)
- Baha temple (wd:Q156813)
- British overseas territories (wd:Q1213)
- Catholic cathedral (wd:Q1213)
- Celticist (wd:Q1213)
- Christian denominations (wd:Q1021566)
- Christian school (wd:Q873148)
- Cloche (wd:Q543750)
- Conservatory of departmental relevance ...
- Ecological conservation immediately ...
- French overseas collectivity (wd:Q173487)
- French ware (wd:Q820533)
- Gendarmerie territoriale (wd:Q13554035)
- Georgian telescope (wd:Q14318)
- Man center (wd:Q1247691)
- Mercury center (wd:Q1683838)
- NDA Weather Radio station ...
- National Monument of the United States ...
- National Park of the United States ...
- National Reserve (wd:Q6978079)
- National Wildlife Refuge (wd:Q110668)
- One Earth Ecoregion (wd:Q12423147)
- Plinian eruption (wd:Q174707)
- Protestant church building (wd:Q10624206)
- Roman Catholic metropolitan archdiocese ...
- Scene (wd:Q1887189)
- Scene Reserve (wd:Q83248369)
- Sikhish Meehangh Aka (wd:Q1798598)
- Sikhish Meehangh Parwana (wd:Q1798598)
- Suitwayan eruption (wd:Q1880842)

Suchspalten: Querynamen Querynamen

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English [en]

SPARQL
Unicorn

Beispiel: Samian Research & Linked Open Samian Ware

```
SPARQL endpoint /n4o/kwkg (see documentation) Example query(es): Please select
1 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
2 PREFIX lido: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
3 SELECT ?item ?geo ?klnregion WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://archaeology.link/ontology#ProductionCentre> .
5 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geo .
6 ?item_geo <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
7 ?item lido:clusteredAs ?kr .
8 ?kr rdfs:label ?klnregion .
9 }
```

Item	geo	klnregion
1 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/hamlin/loc_2000014>	*http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a POINT(5.06667 49.22)* ^{http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a}	'Argonne'Ⓜ
2 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/hamlin/loc_2000014>	*http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a POINT(5.383333 45.833333)* ^{http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a}	'Central Gaulish'Ⓜ
3 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/hamlin/loc_2000014>	*http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a POINT(8.278055999999999 49.118056)* ^{http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a}	'Obergermanisch'Ⓜ
4 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/hamlin/loc_2000014>	*http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a POINT(6.633333 49.25)* ^{http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a}	'East Gaulish'Ⓜ
5 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/hamlin/loc_2000014>	*http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a POINT(7.4 48.533333)* ^{http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a}	'Obergermanisch'Ⓜ
6 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/hamlin/loc_2000014>	*http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a POINT(6.633333 46.25)* ^{http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a}	'Central Gaulish'Ⓜ
7 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/hamlin/loc_2000014>	*http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a POINT(10.666667 48.333333)* ^{http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a}	'Obergermanisch'Ⓜ
8 <http://data.archaeology.link/data/hamlin/loc_2000014>	*http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a POINT(13.083333 44.25)* ^{http://www.opengis.net/def/ows/EPSS/G4326a}	'South Gaulish'Ⓜ

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelper Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlink Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph -> ?item ?geo (GeoSPARQL Endpoint) Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: productioncentre

Valid Query

```
1 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
2 PREFIX lido: <http://archaeology.link/ontology#>
3 SELECT ?item ?geo ?klnregion WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://archaeology.link/ontology#ProductionCentre> .
5 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geo .
6 ?item_geo <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
7 ?item lido:clusteredAs ?kr .
8 ?kr rdfs:label ?klnregion .
9 }
```

Gezeichnete Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

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Beispiel: Samian Research Daten aus dem N4O KG

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph **SPARQL** Collections Repositories Terminologies Manual

SPARQL endpoint: <https://nfdi4objects.org/sparql>

```

1 PREFIX ogham: <http://www.ogham.ie/ontology/ogham.ttl#>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 PREFIX foaf: <http://xmlns.foaf.org/2000/01/01/foaf.ttl#>
4 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
5 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
6 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
7 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
8 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
9 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
10 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
11 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
12 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
13 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
14 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
15 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
16 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
17 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
18 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
19 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>
20 PREFIX nfdi4o: <http://nfdi4objects.org/ontology/nfdi4o.ttl#>

```

Graph visualization showing a network of nodes and edges, with a central node labeled 'NFDI4 OBJECTS'.

SPARQL Unicorn

```

1 PREFIX ogham: <http://www.ogham.ie/ontology/ogham.ttl#>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
3 SELECT ?type ?label ?uri WHERE {
4 ?type ogham:ogham ?uri .
5 ?type rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?type rdfs:label ?label .
7 ?type rdfs:label ?label .
8 ?type rdfs:label ?label .
9 ?type rdfs:label ?label .
10 ?type rdfs:label ?label .
11 ?type rdfs:label ?label .
12 ?type rdfs:label ?label .
13 LIMIT 100
}

```

SPARQL Unicorn

Layer Mincalypso

Beispiel: Linked Open Ogham (Stones) aus dem N4O KG

Samian Research

kuratiert vom
Leibniz-Zentrum für Archäologie (LEIZA)

<http://www.rgzm.de/samian>

left: Vitalis i (red), Samian produced at La Graufesenque, Southern France, Drag. 18
right: Vitalis iii (red), Samian produced at Les Martres-de-Veyre, Central France, Drag. 18
left and right: VITALIS (black) Amphoras produced in Baetica, Southern Spain, Dressel 20

Samian Research, CC BY 4.0

via <https://www1.rgm.de/lips/queries/lipsOutputFull.cfm?selectPottername=Vitalis%20i&selectSite=lyon&selectDie=11d>

Samian Research ID	163465	Decoration Nr	0000000	OCK Vessel Nr	
Tradition	Gaulish-Germanic-Raetian	OCK Potter Nr		Die position	Base inside
Kilnsite	La Graufesenque	Special Reading	VITALIS	Reading Direction	Pro
Potter	Vitalis i (About)	Simple Reading		Form attribute	
Die	11d (Search the Variety of Vitals i)	Findspot	Tiron	Slip colour	
Frame No	0 info			Findspot character	
Date	AD 50-65				
Form	24 (Info)				
Site	Lyon Colonia Augustanum (1) (Photos of 167717)				
Repository site	Lyon	Museum Inv. No		Excavation Nr	
Repository	Musée de la Civilisation Gallo-Romaine				
Amount	1				
Bibliography	Allmer / Dissard 1892, p. 433,1337				
Comment					

Beispiel: Vitalis i

Samian Research, CC BY 4.0

via <https://www1.rezm.de/ips/queries/IPSOutputFull.cfm?selectPottername=Vitalis%20iii&selectSite=Godmanchester&selectDie=6a>

Samian Research ID	153182	Decoration Nr	0000000	OCK Vessel Nr	
Tradition	Gaulish-Germanic-Raetian	OCK Potter Nr		Die position	Base inside
Kiln site	Les Mârtres-de-Veyre	Special Reading	-VITAF·ISFECI	Reading Direction	Pro
Potter	Vitalis iii (About)	Simple Reading		Form attribute	Slip colour
Die	6a ¹⁶ (Single Die Variety of Vitalis iii)	Findspot		Findspot character	
Frame No	0 info	Repository site	Saint Ives	Museum Inv. No	2446
Date	AD 100-125	Repository	Notris Museum	Excavation Nr	
Form	27 (can)	Amount	1		
Site	Godmanchester (1)	Bibliography			
		Comment			

Beispiel: Vitalis iii

Ausschnitt aus der Linked Open Samian Ware Ontology

<https://rgzm.github.io/samian-lod/doc/>

via <https://romanopendata.eu/>

Amphoric Type Title	Area Title	Finding Place Title	Simplified Transcription
Dressel 20	Koenigshoffen	route des Romains	VITALISF
Dressel 20	Lora del Rio	Álamo Alto	VITALIS
Pompei 26	Pompei	30 Mai 1941 in atrio I. VIII. 14	magister M. Lartidius Vitalis domo Clupeis
Pompei 7	Pompei	12 Mai 1954 in caupona II - IV - 1-13	Vitalis
Pompei 7	Pompei	12 Mai 1954 in caupona II - IV - 1-13	Vitalis
Pompei 7	Pompei	12 Mai 1954 in caupona II - IV - 1-13	Vitalis
Dressel 20	Roma	N10 60-80	VITALIS
Dressel 20	Roma	N9 100-120	VITALIS
Dressel 20	Roma	N10 120-150	VITALIS
Dressel 20	Roma	89 N 01-02 (000-030)	VITALIS
Dressel 20	Roma	89 N/S 01-02 (066-090)	VITALIS
Dressel 20	Sauvian	La Domergue	VITALIS
Dressel 20	Strasbourg	Strasbourg	VITALIS & VITALIS...

Amphoren aus dem CEIPAC Dataset Explorer

via <https://romanopendata.eu/>

	AreaTitle	AmphoralIdentifier	AmphoricTypeTitle	SimplifiedTranscription	FullTranscription	FindingPlaceLongitude	FindingPlaceLatitude	FindingPlaceTitle	ProductionDateStartYear	ProductionDateEndYear	ProductionPlaceTitle	ProductionPlaceLatitude	ProductionPlaceLongitude
1	Sauvian	"39737" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALIS	VITALIS, sine imagine	"3.260242" ^{decimal}	"43.292932" ^{decimal}	La Domergue					
2	Strasbourg	"25463" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALIS & VITALIS...	[VITALIS(-?)]	"7.787355" ^{decimal}	"48.600381" ^{decimal}	Strasbourg			Álamo Alto	"37.635985" ^{decimal}	"-5.511535" ^{decimal}
3	Lora del Río	"11093" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALIS	[VI*TA]L-[S]	"-5.52751" ^{decimal}	"37.658961" ^{decimal}	Álamo Alto			Álamo Alto	"37.635985" ^{decimal}	"-5.511535" ^{decimal}
4	Koenigs hofen	"8189" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALISF	[VITALISF]	"7.702305" ^{decimal}	"48.581105" ^{decimal}	route des Romains					
5	Roma	"5767" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALIS	[V]ITAL'IS	"12.483333" ^{decimal}	"41.9" ^{decimal}	89 N 01-02 (000-030)			Álamo Alto	"37.635985" ^{decimal}	"-5.511535" ^{decimal}
6	Roma	"5804" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALIS	[VIT'A]LIS	"12.483333" ^{decimal}	"41.9" ^{decimal}	89 N/S 01-02 (066-090)	"217" ^{int}	"229" ^{int}	Álamo Alto	"37.635985" ^{decimal}	"-5.511535" ^{decimal}
7	Roma	"41350" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALIS	VITALIS	"12.483333" ^{decimal}	"41.9" ^{decimal}	N10 120-150	"220" ^{int}	"224" ^{int}			
8	Roma	"41348" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALIS	VITALIS	"12.483333" ^{decimal}	"41.9" ^{decimal}	N10 60-80	"220" ^{int}	"224" ^{int}			
9	Roma	"41349" ^{int}	Dressel 20	VITALIS	VITALIS	"12.483333" ^{decimal}	"41.9" ^{decimal}	N9 100-120	"220" ^{int}	"224" ^{int}			
10	Pompei	"47372" ^{int}	Pompei 26	magister M. Lartidius Vitalis domo Clupeis	magister M. Lartidius Vitalis domo Clupeis	"14.483333" ^{decimal}	"40.75" ^{decimal}	30 Mai 1941 in atrio I. VIII. 14					
11	Pompei	"47505" ^{int}	Pompei 7	Vitalis	Vitalis	"14.483333" ^{decimal}	"40.75" ^{decimal}	12 Mai 1954 in caupona II - IV - 1-13					
12	Pompei	"47504" ^{int}	Pompei 7	Vitalis	Vitalis	"14.483333" ^{decimal}	"40.75" ^{decimal}	12 Mai 1954 in caupona II - IV - 1-13					
13	Pompei	"47506" ^{int}	Pompei 7	Vitalis	Vitalis	"14.483333" ^{decimal}	"40.75" ^{decimal}	12 Mai 1954 in caupona II - IV - 1-13					

Amphoren aus dem CEIPAC Dataset Explorer

via <https://romanopendata.eu/>

Corpus CEIPAC n° 22190

Inscription data

SimplifiedTranscription	VITALIS & VITALIS...
FullTranscription	[VITALIS(-?)]
ReadingDirectionTitle	Directa
InscriptionPositionTitle	ignotus
InscriptionReliefTitle	litt. extantibus

Corpus CEIPAC n° 7826

Inscription data

SimplifiedTranscription	VITALISF
FullTranscription	[VITALISFI]
ReadingDirectionTitle	Directa
InscriptionPositionTitle	in ansa
InscriptionReliefTitle	litt. extantibus

Beispiel: VITALIS

Nur eine hypothetische CRM-Modellierung!

Ausschnitt aus der EPNet Ontology

(Production and Distribution of Food during the Roman Empire: Economic and Political Dynamics)

<https://romanopendata.eu/sparql/doc/index.html>

Vagheiten modellieren mit dem Academic Meta Tool (AMT)

<https://academic-meta-tool.xyz>

Reading: **SABINI MANVS**
Manus
 (from the hand of Sabinus)

Samian Research, CC BY 4.0
 via <https://www1.rzg.m.de/jps/queries/IPSOutputFull.cfm?selectPottername=Sabinus%20iii&selectSite=La%20Graufesenque&selectDie=MS1a>

Samian Research ID 125149	Decoration Nr 6000182	OCK Vessel Nr
Tradition Gaulish-Germanic-Raetian	Die position Infradecorative	
Kilnsite La Graufesenque and Le Rozier and Banassac?	Special Reading SABIVIMANVS	Reading Direction Pro
Potter Sabinus iii <small>(About)</small>	Simple Reading	Slip colour
Die MS1a ¹²¹ <small>(Graph Die Variety of Sabinus iii)</small>	Form attribute	Findspot character
Frame No 0 <small>Info</small>	Findspot	
Date AD 50-80		
Form Hermet 15 <small>(Lagrive)</small>		
Site La Graufesenque <small>Cerdos/Maguer</small> <small>() *Preston id 246410 Kilnsite</small>		
Repository site La Graufesenque	Museum Inv. No	Excavation Nr. nn
Repository Dépôt de Fouilles		
Amount 1		
Bibliography Bémont et al. 1987, pl.11		
Comment		

Beispiel: Sabinus iii

Reading: *CINNAMI*
 Genitiv
 (from the potter
 OR pottery of Cinnamus)

Samian Research, CC BY 4.0
 via <https://www1.rzgm.de/ips/queries/IPSOutputFull.cfm?selectPottername=Cinnamus%20ii&selectSite=Stonea%20Grange&selectDie=5b>

Samian Research ID 46745	Decoration Nr. 0000000	OCK Vessel Nr.
Tradition Gaulish-Germanic-Raetian		
Kilnsite Lezoux and Lublé and Toulon-sur-Allier and Vichy and Terre-Franche		
Potter Cinnamus ii <small>(About)</small>	OCK Potter Nr.	
Die 5b ²⁹ <small>(Graph Die Variety of Cinnamus ii)</small>	Special Reading CINNAMI	Die position Intradecorative
Frame No. 0 <small>Info</small>	Simple Reading	Reading Direction Ret
Date 135-180	Form attribute	Slip colour
Form 37 <small>(Wheel Decorated)</small>	Findspot	Findspot character
Site Stonea Grange		
Repository site	Museum Inv. No.	Excavation Nr. exc. ST81 PV 228
Repository		
Amount 1		
Bibliography		
Comment		

Beispiel: Cinnamus ii

Independent Potter = T. Iulius Apla(stus).

Tria Nomina (praenomen + gentile name + cognomen)
indicates Roman citizenship or liberated slave.

⇒ Titus, member of the family of the Iulii, called Aplastus

Dependant Potter (lessee) = Primus (written in nominativ)

Chief Potter (lessor) = Petillus (written in genitiv)

What is in a potter's name...

Samian Research, CC BY 4.0

Reading: *MASCLUS.F*
Fecit (made by the potter
Masclus)

Samian Research, CC BY 4.0

Reading: *OF PASSIENI*
Officina (by the workshop
of the potter Passienus)

“Human Person” oder “Company” ?

Linked Open Ogham

kuratiert vom
Research Squirrel Engineers Network

<https://github.com/LinkedOpenOgham/ogham-lod/>

R.A.S. Macalister, Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum, vol. I (1945) / p.502

4.-6. AD early Medieval “Primitive Irish”

Al-qamar / CC BY-SA 3.0 via Wikimedia Commons

Florian Thieri, CC BY 4.0

Ogham!

Irische Ogham-Steine mit Inschriften
des primitive Irish Ogham Script

Florian Thiery, Timo Homburg, Sophie C. Schmidt und Martina Trognitz, CC BY 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons

This project is funded by Wikimedia Deutschland e. V. within the Open Science Fellows Program.

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FELLOWS
PROGRAM**

wmde.org/opensciencefellows

The Linked Open Ogham LOD / Wikidata Workflow

Florian Thiery / Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

153.—(No. VI).

At Chute Hall. Grit, 3' 4" × 1' 0" × 0' 7". Inscription on two diagonally opposed angles, up-down.

CCICAMINI MAQQI CATTINI

Of 4I, all but I¹ is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of CATTINI and the following A. The doubled initial C does not appear to be anything more than an engraver's freak: it would be a mistake to separate CCI from the rest of the names and to equate it to the always enclitic KOI. We shall see a similar beginning at Camp (177).

R.A.S. Macalister, *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, vol. I (1945) / p.1492

Beispiel: CIIC 153 Ballinrannig VI

BALIG/6

Corpus: [Macalister/1897:11](#)

Refs: [Macalister/1945:153](#)

Site: [BALIG](#)

Discovery: recognised, 1782 Pelham, H.

History: According to Macalister/1945, 144, this stone was found 'in an ancient burial-ground, called Kilvickillane, on the shore of Smerwick Bay'. It was subsequently transferred in 1848 to Chute Hall, near Tralee.

Geology: Macalister/1945, 149: 'Grit'

Dimensions: 1.02 x 0.3 x 0.18 (converted from Macalister/1945)

Setting: unattach

Location: other
Macalister/1945, 145--147: 'this stone was found in an ancient burial-ground, called Kilvickillane, on the shore of Smerwick Bay...It was taken to his residence, Chute Hall, near Tralee'.

Form: plain

Condition: complete, some
Macalister/1945, 149, refers to some letters being chipped off the stone.

Folklore: none

Crosses: none

Decorations: no other decoration

References

- [Cuppige/etal/1986](#) 149 drawing concise discussion
- [Macalister/1897](#) 30--31 minor reference
- [Macalister/1945](#) 149 drawing concise discussion

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

via https://www.ucl.ac.uk/archaeology/cisp/database/stone/balig_6.html

Inscriptions

BALIG/6/1

Readings

Macalister, R.A.S. (1897): CCICAMINI MAQQICATTINI
Expansion:
CCICAMINI MAQQI CATTINI
[Macalister/1897](#) 30--31 reading only
[Macalister/1945](#) 149 reading only
[Ziegler/1994](#) 264 reading only

Cuppige, J. (1986): CCICAMINI MAQQI[C]C[A]TTINI
Expansion:
CCICAMINI MAQQI[C]C[A]TTINI
[Cuppige/etal/1986](#) 149 reading only

Notes

Orientation: vertical up down
Position: n/a; aris; n/a; undecorated
Incision: inc
Date: None published
Language: Goidelic (ogham)
Ling. Notes: none
Palaeography: none
Legibility: some

Macalister/1945, 149: 'Of 4l, all but 1l is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of Cattini and the following A. The doubled initial C does not appear to be anything more than an engraver's freak: it would be a mistake to separate CCI from the rest of the names and to equate it to the always enclitic KOI.'

Lines: 2
Carving errors: n
Doubtful: no

Names

- [Ciccamini](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)
- [Cattini](#) (Language: Goidelic; Gender: male)

References

- [Macalister/1897](#) 30--31 drawing concise discussion
- [Macalister/1945](#) 149 drawing concise discussion

Beispiel: CIIC 153 / Ballinrannig VI (CISP-Database)

Ausschnitt aus der Linked Open Ogham Ontology

https://doi.org/10.17175/sb005_010

via https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/153_Ballinrannig_VI

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CIIC 153. Ballinrannig VI (BAILE AN REANNAIGH), Co. Kerry

Site Type
Burial ground and probable ecclesiastical site

Description
Site
"Cillvickillane/Cill Mhíic *Líleáin*: A large, grass-grown, sandy knoll, crowned by a single ogham stone, is located at the base of a small promontory on the S shore of Smervick Harbour. It was here that a storm at the end of the 18th century exposed 7 ogham stones, a possible fragment of an ogham stone, a cross-inscribed stone, a number of graves and quantities of bone, and the ruins of several houses (Windele 1838, 145; Chatterton 1839, 194). Windele's sketch of the site shows the ogham stones set out in a rough semi-circle on top of the mound with a slab-lined grave positioned nearby. Chatterton describes the houses as being beyond the mound nearer the sea. Windele interpreted these as the remains of an ancient village, but it has also been suggested that one of the structures, roughly 20 feet x 12 feet (6 x 3.7m), was a church (Curran no. 21). Lord Ventry removed 6 of the ogham stones from the site in the mid-19th century; nos. 1 to 4 now line the driveway to Burnham House/Colaiste Íde, between Dingle and Ventry, and nos. 5 and 6 are preserved in the grounds of Chute Hall near Tralee. Only no. 7 is still preserved on the original site" (Cuppuge 1986, 250-2).

Monument
"Grif, 1.02m x 0.30m x 0.18m (Converted from Macalister 1945, 149). Some damage evident at the top of the stone.

Text
The inscription is up-top-down, 'on two diagonally opposed angles... Of 4l [MAQO]l, but 11 is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of Cattini and the following A' (Macalister 1945, 149). It is noteworthy that there appears to be slightly extra space left here between the name of the person commemorated CCICAMINI and the following formula word MAQO (represented by 'vac' below). This occasional use of space to separate words in ogham (see also CIIC 119 Monastagart I, Co. Cork) is discussed by Mollat (2011, 290).

Transliteration
CCICAMINivac: MAQO[?] C[A]TTINI

Translation
of C? son of Caltne'

Commentary
• The father's name CATTINI (later Caltne) likewise occurs as the father's name in an inscription found at Ballintaggart (CIIC 157), a site also located in Corca Dhubhíne territory.

Locations
Found
Exposed by a storm at the end of the 18th century, along with 6 other ogham stones (Cuppuge 1986, 250), in the townland of Ballinrannig and barony of Corkaguiney. (GPS coordinates -10.388106, 52.178511)

Original
Find location probably original site

Last Recorded
In the mid 19th century this stone and CIIC 153 were moved by Lord Ventry to Chute Hall, near Tralee, where they remain today. The present location of this stone may be accessed via the National Monuments Service Historic Environment viewer on www.archaeology.ie (GPS coordinates -9.642423, 52.275855)

History of Recording
First recognised in 1782 by Pitham and recorded by Vallancey (1804) in *Collectanea de Rebus Hibernicis* 6, 226 (Macalister 1945, 144). This stone was recorded for the Ogham in 3D project in 2017 by Helena Zacharias, a participant on the Corca Dhubhíne 3d project, using Structure from Motion 3d technology.

References
• Bennett I. and Uí Shéithigh B. (1995). *Ogham Stones of the Dingle Peninsula*. Ballyferrier, pp 7-8.
• Cuppuge, J. et al (1988). *Archaeological Survey of the Dingle Peninsula*. Ballyferrier, pp 250-2.
• Macalister, R.A.S. (1945). *Corpus inscriptionum insularum Celticarum*, pp 144, 149.
• McManus, D. (1991). *A guide to ogham: Maynooth Monographs* 4, p. 108.

Websites and Online Databases
• Corca Dhubhíne 3d: www.corcadhubhine3d.ie
• www.archaeology.ie

Beispiel: CIIC 153 / Ballinrannig VI (Ogham in 3D Repository)

```

<div type="description" n="text">
  <head>Text</head>
  <p>The inscription is up-top-down, <q>on two diagonally opposed angles...
    Of 4I [MAQQI], all but I1 is chipped off, as are also the proximal ends of the C of Cattini and the following A</q> (<ref type="bibliog" target="#MAC1945">
      <date when="1945">1945</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
        >149</biblScope></bibl></ref>. It is noteworthy that there appears to be slightly extra space left here between the name of the person commemorate
    This occasional use of space to separate words in ogham (see also <ref
      target="search.php?ciic=118"
      >CIIC 118</ref> Monataggart I, Co. Cork) is discussed by <ref
        type="bibliog" target="#MOF2011"><bibl><author>Moffat</author> (<date
          when="2011">2011</date>, <biblScope type="pp"
            >290</biblScope></bibl></ref>.
  </p>
</div>

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Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

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  <head xml:lang="en">Transliteration</head>
  <ab>
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    <w lemma="MAQI" type="formula">MAQ/Q<supplied reason="lost">/I</supplied></w>
    <persName><w lemma="CATTINI">C<supplied reason="lost">A</supplied>TTINI</w></persName>
  </ab>
</div>
<div type="translation" xml:lang="en">
  <head>Translation</head>
  <ab><q>of C? son of Caitne</q></ab>
</div>

```


Nur eine hypothetische CRM-Modellierung!

Beispiel: CIIC 153 / Ballinrannig VI (als TEI/EpiDoc)

Finis! Thx!

Questions?

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